

CLASSROOM OBSERVATION TYPES AND COMPONENTS: ITS RELATION TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

This study focused on the types and components of Classroom Observation and its relationship to the Performance of Classroom Teachers in the Sariaya West District of Quezon. Specifically, this study sought answer the following on the perception of the respondents on Clinical or Instructional Observation, Walkthrough Observation and Star Observation; on how the respondents perceived the following components of classroom observation in terms of objectives, procedures, strategy, and post conference; on the level of teachers' respondent performance during the academic year 2019-2020; and find out the significant relationship of teachers' performance and classroom observations and observation components. Analysis of the data gathered revealed that majority of the teacher respondents belong to 26-30 years old; female and 0-5 years length of service; they taught Araling Panlipunan for Grade 1. They are Bachelor's Degree holder and got Very Satisfactory rating performance. They perceived that their school heads practiced Clinical or Instructional Observation, Walkthrough Observation and Situation Task Action Result Observation. Most of them conducted Classroom Observation having the following components Objectives, Procedure, Strategy and Post Conference. In conclusion, the hypotheses stating that teachers' performance is not significantly related to classroom observation types and component types is not supported in this study. Based on the findings of the study found out that classroom observation is significantly correlated to teachers' performance, the school head, Master Teacher and Head Teacher may be encouraged to do a strategic plan on how the teacher be assisted using the typology of classroom observations presented in this study. Further study regarding what type of Classroom Observation should be used during Observation is highly recommended likewise, conduct Learning Action Cell sessions regarding Classroom Observation may be utilized effectively by the school official particularly in this new normal setting of education.

Keywords: Classroom Observation; Clinical Observation; Walkthrough Observation; Situation Task Action Result Observation